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CHEMICAL WASTE OF FOOD INDUSTRIES

Horbatiuk N.,

Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University;

Associate Professor of the Department of Chemistry, Ecology and Methods of Their Education.

Ukraine

Nedaiborshch N.,

Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University;

Lecturer-trainee of the Department of Chemistry, Ecology and Methods of Their Education.

Ukraine

Parakhnenko V.,

Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University;

Lecturer-trainee of the Department of Chemistry, Ecology and Methods of Their Education.

Ukraine

Zadorozhna O.,

Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University;

Associate Professor of the Department of Chemistry, Ecology and Methods of Their Education.

Ukraine

Blahopoluchna A.

Pavlo Tychyna Uman State Pedagogical University;

Lecturer-trainee of the Department of Technologies and Organization of Tourism and Hotel and Restaurant Business.

Ukraine

ABSTRACT

The issue of recovery (utilization) or removal of waste from the food industry is extremely relevant today. Large volumes of daily production of products for various purposes lead to the formation of a huge amount of food waste, including many chemicals that are included in the composition of flavorings, dyes, preservatives, stabilizers, etc. Large cities annually budget sums for the construction and modernization of plants for the processing of organic waste that have become unusable.

However, even this brings only partial results. The more the world population increases, the more food production increases. With the growth of production, the amount of food waste also increases. The increase in the number of open landfills and landfills is proof of that.

Keywords: chemical waste, food production, flavorings, dyes.

Formulation of the problem. Despite the war, the food industry is developing, and the requirements for environmental protection are increasing. The production of food products is accompanied by the formation of liquid, gaseous and solid wastes that pollute water, atmosphere and soil. The main problem of the ecology of food production is the problem of water, where a large amount of chemicals enters.

Analysis of recent research and publications. Wastewater usually contains a complex mixture of insoluble and soluble components of different nature and

concentration. Household waste, as a rule, contain soil and intestinal microflora, including pathogenic ones microorganisms. Domestic sewage and waste from the food industry are particularly harmful because that a lot of oxygen is used to oxidize these substances in water bodies. Industrial enterprises of various industries dump a large amount of poisons into water bodies, including including heavy metals, cyanides [1-3].

The production of food products is accompanied by the formation of liquid, gaseous and solid wastes polluting the hydrosphere, atmosphere and soils. But

the main problem of the ecology of food production is the problem of water. All of them enterprises need a large amount of water, which is used directly in technologies of the main product (brewery, alcohol, sugar), for washing equipment and other purposes [3-5].

Discharge of such water into the city sewage networks are not allowed, and their removal and collection on "filtration fields" leads to the formation of toxic, unpleasant-smelling substances that pollute atmospheric air over a large area [6].

The arrival of contaminated WS containing organic substances of plant and of animal origin into natural reservoirs leads to deterioration of conditions vital activities of hydrobionts as a result of the destruction of these substances oxygen is consumed, which is dissolved in water and is one of the most important conditions vital activities of the biota of water bodies. Yes, one liter of SV distillery, meat processing plant or a cheese factory can "spoil" several thousand liters of river or pond water. Currently, domestic food enterprises have almost no effective ones treatment facilities, and an economic mechanism for ensuring environmental safety is used inefficiently and does not stimulate enterprises to organize sites with cleaning of the SV [7-10].

The use of mechanical, chemical and physico-chemical methods or does not provide the necessary degree of purification of such highly polluted waters, or is quite expensive. The most progressive and rational for these conditions is a biochemical method that ensures the decomposition of the vast majority of complex compounds organic compounds to CO₂ and water

without the use of chemical reagents [11]. Offered a number of technologies for the purification of alcohol, yeast, and milk processing plants productions. Anaerobic-aerobic destruction is the main element of these technologies of pollutants of the SV with the achievement of cleaning efficiency according to BSK of 95-99%. At this stage, methane fermentation occurs in the anaerobic stage with the formation of biogas, which contains up to 80% methane. Considering that from one volume of highly concentrated SVs in the process of methane fermentation produces more than 20 volumes of biogas, the latter is possible to be used as a source of fuel at the enterprise. This will save up to 1/3 fuel resources for the enterprise, which is extremely relevant for Ukrainians enterprises in modern condition [12-15].

The purpose of the work. To analyze the ways of environmental diseases caused by chemical substances of food products. Determine which food businesses are the biggest polluters of wastewater.

Results. Industrial waste is divided into two categories: supporting waste due to the use of biotechnological processes (food production products, beverages, fermentation, etc.) and chemical industry waste. Food industry waste has a different chemical composition and can to be processed by biological oxidation with use specialized cultures of microorganisms.

Part of the waste from food production has such a chemical composition that allows you to obtain secondary products from them and use them as raw materials for biofuel.

Table 1.

Chemical composition of grain production waste

Type of raw material	Lipids	Cellulose	Ash	Protein
Waste of oats	0,50	48,80	4,30	5,20
Waste of rice	2,00	38,60	16,90	5,20
Waste of buckwheat	1,60	29,40	5,00	4,09

Table 2.

Chemical composition of coffee sludge

Coffee oil	Cellulose and lignin	Caffeol	Proteins
7-12%	60-75%	3-5%	5-7%

Table 3.

Chemical composition of grape pomace

Cellulose	Hemicelluloses	Pectin substances	Lignin	"Raw" protein	"Raw" fat	Tanneries substances	Mineral substances
22,3%	12,9%	0,7%	35,4%	18,8%	1,4%	1,8%	3,1%

All enterprises need a large amount of water, which is used directly in the technology of the main product (brewery, alcohol, sugar), for washing equip-

ment and other purposes. Most of this water is discharged from the process and into the environment in the form of contaminated effluents.

Fig. 1. The average annual amount of wastewater at food enterprises

The average annual amount of wastewater (SW) at food enterprises is (m³): 2.9 per 1 ton of bakery products; per 1 ton of beets in sugar production – 1.7; per 1000 dal of beer – 76; per 1t of pressed baker's yeast - 170; for 1000 dal of alcohol - 1300.

A significant part of these wastewaters is represented by highly polluted waters, characterized by the value of CHC (chemical oxygen consumption) from 2000 to 60000 mgO₂/dm³

Their main feature is a high content of dissolved organic substances. It is not allowed to discharge such water into the city sewer networks, and its removal and collection in "filtration fields" leads to the formation of toxic, unpleasant-smelling substances that pollute the atmospheric air over a large area. The meat, sugar, alcohol and yeast industries of the food industry have the greatest negative impact on the environment.

Food industries often use dyes, and they are often of synthetic origin. Getting into wastewater, these dyes form a cocktail of chemical compounds. For example, Ponceau 4R (food additive E 124) is a dye of synthetic origin that has a bright red color.

According to its chemical composition, the E 124 dye is a sodium salt: a red granulate or powder that is well soluble in water. Chemical formula of dye E 124: C₂₀H₁₁N₂Na₃O₁₀S₃. Additive E 124 is thermostable, resistant to light, reducing agents and oxidizing agents. Products processed by Ponceau can be subjected to any technological operations (sterilization, pasteurization, cooling, freezing, etc.).

Ponceau (additive E 124) is widely used (independently or in combination with other dyes) in the coloring of products in the confectionery industry, in the production of beverages, ice cream, puddings, desserts, fruit preserves. Additive E 124 is used in the production of fish and meat products, dairy desserts, cakes and cheese products. In the USA, Finland, Norway and some other countries, dye E 124 (Ponsot 4R) is included in the list of prohibited substances as a carcinogen that can cause the development of cancer. In addition, the additive E 124 is a strong allergen, and can

cause anaphylactic shock, or an attack of hay fever in asthmatics and people with an intolerance to aspirin.

Flavorings are food additives that are added to a food product to give it aroma and taste. By composition, flavorings are a mixture of flavoring substances with or without a solvent or a dry carrier (filler), or an individual flavoring substance.

According to their chemical structure, aromatic substances belong to different classes of organic compounds: aliphatic and aromatic hydrocarbons, of which terpenes and their oxygen-containing derivatives (terpenoids) predominate - alcohols, acids, ethers and esters, aldehydes and ketones.

Depending on the requirements for the taste and aroma of the finished technological flavoring, proteins and amino acids (extracts of pork, beef, lamb or poultry meat), carbohydrates (ribose, xylose, arabinose, glucose, fructose, sucrose and others) are used, fats (vegetable fats and oils, animal or fish), other additives such as monosodium glutamate, nucleotides, food acids, sodium chloride, fillers, carriers of functional aromatic substances. Aromatic substances are formed during the Mayard reaction during heat treatment for 15 minutes at a temperature not exceeding 180°C. Technological flavorings are used in meat and fish products, vegetable processing products, mushrooms, fast food products, in sauces, for sprinkling chips, croutons, etc.

One of the most important requirements in food production is the cleanliness and hygiene of the use of equipment, inventory and consumables. For this production is used certified technical detergents for the food industry: alkaline, acidic, neutral. Means are washed away, together with waste water, they fall into reservoirs, where they can cause considerable damage to the environment, disrupting aquatic ecosystems. Many chemicals that can be included in the composition of the product pass through water treatment systems without obstacles and enter the city water supply system.

All the factors described above are very harmful to the environment. As we can see, the food industry is a major polluter of ecosystems

Conclusions. It has been established that a number of wastes are generated in the process of food production. Some of them are safe and suitable for further processing into animal feed or biofuel. The rest of the waste is harmful chemicals that, together with wastewater, enter water bodies, polluting ecosystems. The most dangerous are waste with synthetic aromas, dyes and detergents, so it is necessary to improve the technological processes of the production of waste products and modernize the lines for better cleaning of chemical waste.

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